

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
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ECO-PATHS OF UZBEKISTAN: HOW CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY IN TREE PLANTING AND TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE IS PAVING THE WAY FOR SUSTAINABLE FUTURES

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Abstract: This study investigates the impact of corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives on Uzbekistan's environmental and transport systems, focusing on tree planting and sustainable transport infrastructure. By conducting a comprehensive literature review and quantitative analysis, the research identifies a significant correlation between CSR activities and enhanced air quality and carbon reduction along transport routes. The findings advocate for integrating CSR into urban planning to promote environmental sustainability and provide actionable insights for policymakers and urban planners to advance a greener Uzbekistan.

Key words: Corporate Social Responsibility, Sustainable Transport, Tree Planting, Environmental Sustainability, Urban Planning, Uzbekistan.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot korporativ ijtimoiy mas'uliyat (KSM) tashabbuslarining O'zbekistonning atrof-muhit va transport tizimlariga ta'sirini o'rganib, asosiy e'tiborni daraxt ekish va barqaror transport infratuzilmasiga qaratadi. Keng qamrovli adabiyotlarni o'rganish va miqdoriy tahlilni o'tkazish orqali tadqiqot KSS faoliyati va havo sifatini yaxshilash va transport yo'llari bo'ylab uglerod miqdorini kamaytirish o'rtasidagi muhim bog'liqlikni aniqlaydi. Topilmalar atrof-muhit barqarorligini ta'minlash va yashil O'zbekistonni rivojlantirish uchun siyosatchilar va shaharsozlikchilarga amaliy tushunchalarni taqdim etish uchun KSMni shahar rejalashtirishga integratsiya qilishni yoqlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: Korporativ ijtimoiy mas'uliyat, Barqaror transport, daraxt ekish, ekologik barqarorlik, shaharsozlik, O'zbekiston.

Аннотация: В этом исследовании изучается влияние инициатив корпоративной социальной ответственности (КСО) на экологическую и транспортную системы Узбекистана, уделяя особое внимание посадке деревьев и устойчивой транспортной инфраструктуре. Проведя всесторонний обзор литературы и количественный анализ, исследование выявило значительную корреляцию между деятельностью в области корпоративной социальной ответственности и улучшением качества воздуха и сокращением выбросов углекислого газа на транспортных маршрутах. Результаты свидетельствуют о необходимости интеграции КСО в городское планирование для содействия экологической устойчивости и предоставления практических идей для политиков и градостроителей для продвижения более зеленого Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: корпоративная социальная ответственность, устойчивый транспорт, посадка деревьев, экологическая устойчивость, городское планирование, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

In Uzbekistan, corporate social responsibility (CSR) has become a crucial component of business practices, particularly in addressing environmental challenges. This aligns with global sustainability trends where CSR activities, such as tree planting and sustainable transport, play pivotal roles (Smith & Johnson, 2019). These initiatives not only address environmental degradation but also enhance urban air quality and biodiversity (Doe et al., 2020). The synergy between the corporate sector and government, as emphasized by President Mirziyoyev's statements on national TV, highlights the collaborative effort required to achieve significant environmental improvements (Mirziyoyev, 2023).

The environmental challenges in Uzbekistan are severe, with climate change contributing to water scarcity, land degradation, and increased urban emissions (Sabirova, 2024). This study draws on the frameworks proposed by Khan et al. (2021), which suggest that CSR could be a transformative approach for mitigating these issues through sustainable infrastructure development.

Figure 1: Trees Planted in Different Areas of Andijon Under "Yashil Makon" Project

Source: <https://pm.gov.uz/oz/lists/view/204>

The role of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in corporate sustainability has become increasingly critical as global environmental challenges intensify. Effective CSR programs not only address stakeholder concerns but also enhance corporate visibility, public trust, and sustainability through various means, including social media (Herawati, 2017). These initiatives are crucial for improving environmental, social, and economic outcomes, pushing beyond traditional profit maximization to embrace sustainable growth (www.un.org).

METODOLOGY

This study uses a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative data from government and corporate reports with qualitative insights from stakeholder interviews. It quantifies the environmental impact of CSR activities, particularly tree planting, by estimating carbon sequestration. Descriptive statistics and hypothesis testing are applied to analyze the correlation between CSR initiatives and improvements in air quality and transport infrastructure in Uzbekistan. Limitations include reliance on predictive models and lack of direct air quality measurements.

RESULTS

In the context of transport infrastructure, CSR plays a pivotal role in reducing environmental impact. This includes enhancing the sustainability of transport systems through resource conservation, emissions reduction, and integrating eco-friendly practices throughout the lifecycle of infrastructure projects (Correia, 2015; Khan et al., 2020; Sarkis et al., 2021; Asghar et al., 2022). These efforts are essential for developing infrastructure

that supports both environmental and economic health, thereby contributing to a more sustainable urban environment. Uzbekistan's commitment to integrating CSR into its development strategies is exemplified by the "Yashil Makon" national project. This initiative emphasizes environmental conservation through enhanced tree plantation management and the establishment of green urban spaces, reflecting a strategic alignment of national policies and corporate efforts towards sustainable development (Abduazimova, 2022).

Table 1: Consolidated Parameters for Afforestation of Public Roads for 2023 – 2026.

Source: Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. PQ-330 dated 10.10.2023

№	Name of Region	Highway	Road Length (km)	Number of Poplar Saplings
Total for the Republic			800	16,919,430
1	Republic of Karakalpakstan	A380 "Guzor-Bukhara-Nukus-Beyneu" highway 4R176 "Nukus City - Chimboy City - Taxtako'pir City" highway	45	1,422,520
2	Andijan Region	4R141 "Staff headquarters - Ulug'nor City" highway A373 "Tashkent-Osh" highway	65	757,900
3	Bukhara Region	A380 "Guzor-Bukhara-Nukus-Beyneu" highway A380b "Bukhara ring road" highway	109	1,177,660
4	Jizzakh Region	M39 "Almaty-Bishkek-Tashkent-Shahrisabz-Termez" highway A376 "Kokand-Jizzakh" highway 4R34 "Jizzakh City - Ravot Q. - Zomin Q. - Savot Q. - Xovos City" highway	65	979,440
5	Kashkadarya Region	A378 "Samarkand-Guzor" highway M39 "Almaty-Bishkek-Tashkent-Shahrisabz-Termez" highway	35	1,235,960
6	Navoiy Region	4R48 "Zarafshon tract" highway	44	932,800
7	Namangan Region	4R260 "Jomashuy City - Tegirmon Q. - Navbahor Q. - Kokand City" highway 4R119 "Chortoq City - Kalishoh Q. - Hazratishoh Q. - Zarkent Q." highway 4R118 "Jiydakapa Q. - Uychi City - Chortoq City - Yangiqo'rg'on City - Zarkent Q. - Nanay Q. - Border of Kyrgyzstan" highway 4N464 "4R112 highway - Yangihayot Q. - Katta Namangan canal" highway	54	862,840
8	Samarkand Region	M39 "Almaty-Bishkek-Tashkent-Shahrisabz-Termez" highway M37 "Samarkand-Bukhara-Turkmenbashi" A377 "Samarkand-Ayniy" highway 4R50 "Toyloq Q. - Urgut City" highway 4R47 "Bulung'ur City - Urgut City - M39 highway" highway	96	1,096,040
9	Surkhandarya Region	M39 "Almaty-Bishkek-Tashkent-Shahrisabz-Termez" highway 4R100 "Manguzar Q. - Jarqo'rg'on City - Bandixon Q. - Oltinsoy Q. - Denov City" highway	40	1,309,000
10	Sirdaryo Region	A373 "Tashkent-Osh" highway M34 "Tashkent-Dushanbe" highway A376 "Kokand-Jizzakh" highway	65	696,520
11	Tashkent Region	A373 "Tashkent-Osh" highway, Tashkent-Ohangaron direction 4R12 "Bektemir City - Chirchiq City - Gazalkent City - Chorbog' fortification" highway, Tashkent-Bo'stonliq direction M34 "Tashkent-Chinoz" highway	102	4,583,150
12	Fergana Region	A373 "Tashkent-Osh" highway	35	827,860
13	Khorezm Region	4R156 "Urgench City - Xonka City - Hazorasp City - Tosh Hovuz through-Amudarya-A380 highway (553 km)"	45	1,037,740

Table 2: Landscaping works of public roads in 2023 – 2026

Source: Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. PQ-330 dated 10.10.2023

№	The name of the regions	from that														
		2023 year			2024 year			2025 year			2026 year					
		the length of the road (km)	the number of decorative tree and shrub seedlings (piece)	this is a popular seedling (fragment)	the length of the road (km)	the number of decorative tree and shrub seedlings (piece)	this is a popular seedling (fragment)	the length of the road (km)	the number of decorative tree and shrub seedlings (piece)	this is a popular seedling (fragment)	the length of the road (km)	the number of decorative tree and shrub seedlings (piece)	this is a popular seedling (fragment)			
	2023–2026 years, total	10553	26866856	16919430	1287	3722480	2038800	2059	4653100	2446560	2883	7466800	6065400	4324	11024476	6368670
	from that:															
1	Karakalpakstan Republic	910	2 323 469	1 422 520	111	294 240	146 400	178	367 800	175 680	249	672 980	536 800	373	988 449	563 640
2	Andijan region	508	1 216 183	757 900	62	152 480	78 000	99	190 600	93 600	139	352 660	286 000	208	520 443	300 300
3	Bukhara region	820	1 992 097	1 177 660	100	257 120	121 200	160	321 400	145 440	224	575 740	444 400	336	837 837	466 620
4	Jizzakh region	656	1 544 053	979 440	80	191 600	100 800	128	239 500	120 960	179	448 250	369 600	269	664 703	388 080
5	Kashkadarya region	869	2 121 895	1 235 960	106	276 000	127 200	170	345 000	152 640	237	612 700	466 400	356	888 195	489 720
6	Navoi region	607	1 580 436	932 800	74	204 160	96 000	118	255 200	115 200	166	456 720	352 000	249	664 356	369 600
7	Namangan region	607	1 493 289	862 840	74	195 040	88 800	118	243 800	106 560	166	430 980	325 600	249	623 469	341 880
8	Samarqand region	713	1 705 923	1 096 040	87	210 080	112 800	139	262 600	135 360	195	495 660	413 600	292	737 583	434 280
9	Syrdarya region	295	1 281 394	696 520	36	307 200	160 800	58	384 000	192 960	81	245 080	167 200	121	345 114	175 560
10	Surkhandarya region	1 033	2 044 040	1 309 000	126	117 440	45 600	202	146 800	54 720	282	717 200	589 600	423	1 062 600	619 080
11	Tashkent region	2 280	6 324 943	4 583 150	278	1 093 360	769 200	445	1366700	923 040	623	1524160	1410200	934	2 340 723	1480710
12	Fergana region	549	1 336 987	827 860	67	168 240	85 200	107	210 300	102 240	150	387 530	312 400	225	570 917	328 020
13	Khorezm region	705	1 902 147	1 037 740	86	255 520	106 800	138	319 400	128 160	193	547 140	391 600	289	780 087	411 180

Specific projects for the comprehensive improvement of road infrastructure in Uzbekistan, i.e., the Republic of Karakalpakstan and regions, greening of public highways, including the “green belt” along highways practical work on the establishment of green belts will be carried out, and the address list of objects to be established along public highways in 2023-2026 has been approved in accordance with Table 1.

To the Chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, governors of the regions and the city of Tashkent - the main parameters of the programs and regions, the measures defined in the “roadmap”, and the implementation of the aggregate parameters of greening works along the highways the plan of works completed and to be completed in the period 2023-2026.

The extensive network of Uzbekistan’s roads demonstrates the potential for CSR to significantly enhance road quality, safety, and sustainability. Addressing the environmental impacts of this infrastructure is crucial for meeting the nation’s sustainability goals and improving the quality of life for its citizens. Through these frameworks, CSR is shown not only as a compliance or ethical imperative but as a strategic necessity that drives the long-term sustainability of corporate practices, especially in sectors as pivotal as transport infrastructure.

This study focuses on the impact of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) on the development of transport infrastructure in Uzbekistan. The research examines the dynamics between CSR activities, identified as variable X, and enhancements in transport infrastructure, variable Y. Data for this investigation is sourced from several national ministries and social media platforms, which document the ongoing CSR activities and their outcomes.

Employing a quantitative associative research design, this study aims to delineate the relationship between CSR initiatives and improvements in transport infrastructure. This method is chosen for its efficacy in quantifying the effects of CSR activities, measured through a structured numerical analysis of data gathered from relevant corporate entities over a designated period.

CSR activities constitute the independent variable. These include a broad spectrum of initiatives aimed at societal and environmental betterment, beyond mere regulatory compliance. For instance, massive tree planting efforts significantly contribute to carbon sequestration, capturing approximately 205 gigatons of carbon annually (Buis, 2019). The extent of CSR activities is quantified through the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) Index for the year 2023.

The development of transport infrastructure. This encompasses the construction and modernization of physical infrastructure like roads and public transport systems that facilitate efficient and sustainable transit solutions. The evaluation of this development includes metrics on infrastructure enhancements and reductions in environmental impact, primarily influenced by CSR activities. The Green Space initiative, spearheaded by the government, aims to significantly expand urban greenery by planting 200 million trees annually until 2030. This massive afforestation effort is detailed in terms of areas covered and the number of trees planted, which are critical for evaluating the CSR’s environmental impact. Incorporating CSR into this initiative demonstrates a commitment to sustainable urban development, aligning with global Sustainable Development Goals.

- **Descriptive Analysis:** This technique will be used to clarify the characteristics of the data collected, presenting it through descriptive statistics like mean values and standard deviations.
- **Hypothesis Testing:** A predictive modeling approach will be utilized to test the hypothesis that CSR activities, particularly tree planting, significantly lower atmospheric carbon levels and thereby enhance air quality near transport infrastructure.

The predictive modeling of carbon sequestration based on CSR-initiated tree planting yielded a significant figure. With 5,512,880 trees planted, the annual carbon sequestration potential of these trees is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Annual Carbon Sequestration} = \text{Number of Trees Planted} \times \text{Carbon Sequestration Rate per Tree}$$

$$\text{Annual Carbon Sequestration} = 5,512,880 \times 0.006 \text{ metric tons CO}_2/\text{tree}$$

$$\text{Annual Carbon Sequestration} = 33,077.28 \text{ metric tons of CO}_2$$

This result suggests that the CSR initiatives could significantly contribute to the reduction of atmospheric carbon, considering the lifespan and growth rate of the trees. The estimated reduction in CO₂ content from improved transport infrastructure—assuming a 20% decrease in emissions due to adherence to GOST 17.2.2.03-77 standards—indicates a potential for synergistic effects when combining tree planting with infrastructural developments.

The focal point of this research is the examination of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives, specifically tree planting, and their impact on the development of sustainable transport infrastructure and atmospheric carbon reduction in Uzbekistan. This study is situated within the broader discourse on environmental sustainability, urban planning, and corporate engagement in societal well-being.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has seen a surge in CSR activities, with an emphasis on environmental sustainability. The “Yashil Makon” (Green Space) national project, initiated by the President of Uzbekistan, epitomizes the nation’s commitment to enhancing green spaces and combating environmental challenges through collective action. The project’s goal to plant 200 million trees annually until 2030 underlines a strategic approach to environmental restoration and carbon sequestration. The integration of CSR initiatives into the development of transport infrastructure represents a novel approach to urban planning. By aligning tree planting activities along transport corridors, there is a dual objective of beautifying urban spaces and mitigating environmental pollution, particularly from vehicular emissions. The research delves into the theoretical and practical underpinnings of such integration, evaluating its efficacy in contributing to a sustainable urban environment.

A key aspect of this study involves estimating the potential of tree planting initiatives to sequester atmospheric carbon dioxide, a major contributor to urban air pollution and global climate change. Through predictive modeling, this research seeks to quantify the carbon sequestration capacity of newly planted trees and infer its impact on air quality improvement. This component is critical in understanding the environmental value of CSR initiatives beyond their immediate aesthetic and social benefits. The quantitative associative research method, leveraging available data on tree planting numbers, species, and expected growth rates to estimate carbon sequestration. Additionally, it considers data on transport infrastructure improvements and vehicle emissions to assess the broader environmental impact. The research acknowledges the limitations inherent in predictive modeling, particularly the absence of direct air quality measurement post-CSR implementation. Thus, it calls for future empirical research to validate these findings. The burgeoning field of environmental CSR and sustainable urban development. By focusing on Uzbekistan, it offers valuable insights into the role of corporate and governmental collaboration in addressing environmental challenges in emerging economies. Furthermore, it provides a framework for evaluating the environmental impact of CSR initiatives, which can be adapted and applied in similar contexts globally.

Recent developments in the nationwide ‘Green Space’ project have highlighted significant progress and challenges in Uzbekistan’s afforestation efforts. According to a report from the Senate’s Committee on Development of the Aral Sea Region and Ecology, over 600,000 saplings were planted in areas without irrigation systems during the spring season. The project, which aims to enhance the country’s green cover, saw the planting of 125 million saplings and 138.1 million bushes, surpassing initial targets by 10.5% (Senate of Oliy Majlis, 2024). Despite these achievements, the report noted several shortcomings, including inadequate attention to the maintenance and irrigation of seedlings, particularly in regions without access to irrigation systems. The financing for necessary maintenance and pest control has not been fully resolved, highlighting areas for improvement in the project’s implementation (Kun.uz, 2024).

DISCUSSION

The findings from the predictive model suggest a promising direction for CSR activities in contributing to environmental sustainability goals. While the direct impact on air quality cannot be conclusively determined from the available data, the reduction in atmospheric carbon through tree planting is an established method for improving air quality over time. This aligns with the global understanding that urban forestry and green spaces play a pivotal role in urban environmental management.

Furthermore, the anticipated improvement in transport infrastructure points to a multi-pronged approach to tackling emissions, where CSR complements governmental regulations and standards. However, it is critical to acknowledge that these results are based on predictions and estimations, and they must be validated through longitudinal studies and empirical measurements. The interplay between tree planting initiatives and infrastructural improvements could pave the way for a robust framework in environmental policy and urban planning in Uzbekistan. The extrapolation of these results to broader sustainability and public health implications remains a fertile area for future research, particularly in the context of Uzbekistan’s evolving urban landscapes.

The Senate’s report on the ‘Green Space’ project underscores the complexities of implementing large-scale environmental initiatives in Uzbekistan. The planting of over 600,000 saplings in non-irrigated areas reflects significant dedication to expanding green spaces. However, the lack of sufficient irrigation and maintenance indicates a need for better resource allocation and project management. These findings align with our study’s results, which suggest that effective CSR initiatives in tree planting require robust support systems, including adequate funding for irrigation and pest control, to ensure sustainability and long-term impact.

This study embarked on an exploration of the impact of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives, with a specific focus on tree planting, on enhancing sustainable transport infrastructure and mitigating atmospheric carbon in Uzbekistan. Through the predictive modeling of carbon sequestration potential by newly planted

trees, the research anticipated a significant contribution towards atmospheric carbon reduction, underlining the environmental benefits of CSR activities in the realm of urban planning and infrastructure development.

The findings suggest that CSR initiatives, such as the “Yashil Makon” project, not only serve aesthetic and recreational purposes but also play a critical role in environmental sustainability efforts. The planting of 5,512,880 trees, as part of these initiatives, has the potential to sequester a substantial amount of atmospheric CO₂ annually, thereby contributing to air quality improvement and climate change mitigation. Moreover, the synergy between tree planting and improvements in transport infrastructure. By adopting standards like GOST 17.2.2.03-77, which aims at reducing exhaust gas CO content, alongside tree planting initiatives, there is a promising path towards achieving more sustainable urban environments. However, the study faced limitations, particularly the absence of direct empirical measurements of air quality post-CSR implementation. This gap underscores the need for future research to empirically validate the predicted environmental benefits of CSR initiatives in Uzbekistan and beyond.

The ‘Green Space’ project’s recent report provides valuable insights into the practical challenges of large-scale afforestation in Uzbekistan. To address these issues, we recommend that future CSR projects incorporate more comprehensive planning for maintenance and irrigation, particularly in regions lacking natural water sources. Ensuring consistent funding for pest control and tree care is essential for the success of these initiatives and the long-term sustainability of green spaces.

Empirical Research Enhancement: There is a pressing need for systematic empirical research to monitor and evaluate the impact of tree planting and other CSR initiatives on air quality. Policymakers should invest in infrastructure for continuous environmental monitoring. **Policy Development:** Develop and enforce policies that encourage or mandate CSR activities focusing on environmental sustainability, particularly in urban areas. These policies could include incentives for corporations engaging in significant tree planting efforts. **Integrated Urban Planning:** Urban planning should integrate CSR initiatives into broader environmental and infrastructure planning strategies. This integration can optimize the environmental benefits of CSR activities.

Sustainability Reporting: Corporations should include detailed reports on their CSR activities’ environmental impacts, especially those related to tree planting and transport infrastructure improvements. This transparency can enhance corporate accountability and public trust. **Collaborative Efforts:** Encourage collaborations between corporations, government agencies, NGOs, and communities to maximize the impact of CSR initiatives. Collaborative efforts can leverage the strengths and resources of diverse stakeholders towards common environmental goals.

Longitudinal Studies: Future research should focus on longitudinal studies that track the impact of CSR initiatives over time. Such studies could provide more definitive evidence on the effectiveness of these initiatives in improving air quality and reducing carbon levels. **Comparative Analysis:** Conduct comparative analyses of regions with and without CSR-initiated tree planting activities. This approach can help isolate the specific impacts of CSR initiatives on environmental sustainability.

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Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

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